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Does the use of Aspirin, Ibuprofen, Naproxen, Acetaminophen (Paracetamol) and similar drugs influence the immune response in the context of vaccination against Sars-CoV-2?

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Abstract

A confused public questions whether painkillers and antipyretics have a negative effect in the context of vaccination against Sars-CoV-2. The honest answer is that there is no scientific consensus on this. So what should be communicated to patients in a primary care setting?

The situation

Educational brochures of health authorities in many countries, which people receive prior to their vaccination against Sars-CoV-2 (regardless of the type of vaccine administered) often recommend the use of over-the-counter painkillers such as ibuprofen, naproxen, aspirin or paracetamol (acetaminophen) to manage mild (normal) vaccination reactions such as muscle pain or an elevated body temperature.

These substances are widely used around the world to counteract the flu-like side effects of fever, headache, general pain, fatigue, and myalgia associated with a variety of conditions. However, extensive reporting (most often not scientific in nature) on the potential side effects of COVID-19 vaccines may cause some people to panic and take these drugs in advance, for example, to be ready for work after vaccination. The drugs are freely available and can therefore be used by anyone as they see fit. But this can be a mistake, not only because far fewer people actually experience adverse vaccine reactions. However, for most vaccinated individuals, especially those who received an mRNA vaccine (currently approved: Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna), the process of immunization proceeded without any significant symptom. Therefore, a hasty intake of antipyretic and analgesic drugs is usually useless nonsense.

Findings

Recently a research group led by Mahyar Etminan at the University of British Columbia has published¹ that painkillers and fever reducers might perhaps weaken the necessary immune response after vaccination. In doing so, the study group points to a randomized trial in the journal THE LANCET that found concomitant use of acetaminophen to prevent adverse events during vaccination in a cohort of children significantly decreased antibody titers compared with controls.²

The Canadian group also cites the U.S. Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), which, in line with the World Health Organization (WHO), does not recommend taking antipyretics and painkillers prior to or immediately at the time of vaccination, but says there is nothing wrong with them a while after the vaccination needle did its job. Whether nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as ibuprofen, aspirin, naproxen, and diclofenac can generally affect immune responses after any vaccinations remains unresolved because the immune systems of people are so extremely different and their functioning dependent on so many co-factors that comparisons between individuals are hard to interpret.

It has long been speculated that suppression of prostaglandin synthesis not only effectively attenuates the flu-like reactions after vaccination, but also reduces the achievable level of vaccine titer. However, due to all the limiting factor regarding this subject the scientific community is still far away from a consensus on this matter. A 2014 paper described that administration of acetaminophen a few hours after vaccination had no effect on the immune response, while immediate administration after vaccination could attenuate it.³

Conclusion

As long as this question, which is important for billions of people, continues to be insufficiently solidly clarified, common sense will apparently have to suffice:

Recommend the discussed substances

- only if necessary
- in as small a dose as possible
- for as short as possible

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Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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